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Optimal sizing of a hybrid OTEC-diesel system with battery energy storage for fish farming application

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Abstract

Aquaculture is the fastest-growing food production system in the world, and it is expected that this sector will meet most of the growing global food demand. Fisheries and aquaculture farms need a smooth and reliable power supply, as any interruption in electricity might result in the complete loss of farm operations. Currently, these farms are highly reliant on fossil fuels. However, Ocean Renewable Energy can power both onshore and offshore aquaculture, reducing environmental effects by supplying power at sea and reducing the need for diesel fuel. Ocean thermal energy is a predictable source of energy that is available year-round, and these characteristics make OTEC a reliable power supply for offshore fish farms. The present study aims to determine the optimal techno-economic sizing of a standalone hybrid OTEC-diesel system with battery energy storage under three different scenarios. The reliability index is calculated to assess the energy system's capability for uninterrupted operation. Additionally, the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) is evaluated to estimate the cost-effectiveness of the proposed energy system. The results indicated that increasing the scale of the hybrid system not only lowers the LCOE but also decreases energy wastage, thereby offering a more economically viable solution and competitive alternative to traditional diesel generator-powered fish farms.

Keywords: OTEC, Battery energy system, Optimization, Sizing, Techno-economic

1. Introduction

Considering population growth and increases in income, global food security projection studies estimated that global food demand will rise by 35% to 56% between 2010 and 2050 [1]. Since 1950, there has been an eight-fold increase in global fish supply. By comparison, despite the Green Revolution, global rice production only experienced a threefold growth. Fish production has experienced rapid growth over the past four decades, making it the fastest-growing sector in the global food market. It is expected that this trend will continue in the foreseeable future, and this sector meets most of the growing demand for food [2]. The aquaculture industry, which traditionally depends on diesel for energy, is also projected to experience global growth. It provides an opportunity to decrease greenhouse gas emissions by transitioning to renewable energy sources. As industry shifts further offshore into more dynamic environments, the opportunity to co-locate offshore aquaculture with marine energy sources becomes feasible [3].

Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion (OTEC) is a technology that uses the temperature difference between the deep cold and relatively warmer surface waters of the ocean to generate electricity. In this process, warm seawater is used to vaporize a low boiling point liquid, such as ammonia. The resulting vapor drives a turbine to produce electricity.

Cold deep seawater is then used to condense the vapor back into a liquid, completing the cycle [4]. Ocean thermal energy is a consistent and predictable energy source available throughout the year, making OTEC a dependable power supply for offshore fish farms.

While technological advancements are crucial for OTEC development, a thorough understanding of its economic viability, especially for small-scale OTEC, is equally essential, given its low efficiency and high capital costs. Wang et al. [5] performed a techno-economic analysis of an OTEC system, examining the LCOE and exergy efficiency for six different working fluids. The results demonstrated that using R717 led to the most advantageous outcomes, achieving LCOE of \$0.34 per kWh and an exergy efficiency of 28.17% with a net output power of 565kW. A method for ensuring the economic viability of OTEC systems by considering different heat source conditions in 16 countries and regional economic conditions is introduced in [6]. It also examines the capacity and type of power plants. For a 1MW class OTEC demonstration plant operating in a closed cycle, the initial investment and 20-year total operating costs are estimated to be around \$17,920,000. Jung et al. [7] examined a 20kW OTEC pilot plant utilizing the Rankine cycle with R22 as the circulating fluid through a modified productive structure analysis. The research revealed LCOE of approximately 0.363 \$/kWh, considering 10kW of energy used for pumping warm surface water and cold deep water, while assuming the unit cost of warm seawater to be zero.

In this study, our aim is to optimally size a hybrid OTEC-Diesel system with battery energy storage to minimize the levelized cost of energy while ensuring uninterrupted farm operation. To achieve this, we first establish the system configuration and then present the mathematical models for the various components of the proposed system. Following this, we formulate the optimization problem, considering both system reliability and cost. Finally, we present and discuss the results of our analysis.

2. System Configuration and Mathematical Modeling

Fig. 1 illustrates the configuration of the proposed stand-alone hybrid system. The system integrates an OTEC unit as the primary power source and a diesel generator as a backup power source, with batteries serving as energy storage devices. In off-grid hybrid systems, incorporating dump loads is essential to dissipate excess power when the batteries are fully charged, and additional power is unnecessary.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the proposed hybrid renewable energy system

2.1. Load demand

Overall, there is a scarcity of data from the aquaculture industry regarding specific energy requirements, especially for offshore systems. Within the aquaculture sector, energy demand varies greatly by operation and species [8]. In this study, the load demand information was collected from a potential fish farm project in South Florida. It consists of 8 net pens with a daily average energy consumption of 11kWh. Energy requirements include vessel movement, feeding, monitoring, and cleaning. It is assumed that cleaning is done once a month, and two hours are needed to clean the net. The seasonal variation of daily power consumption per component of the fish farm is demonstrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Daily energy consumption of a fish farm in different seasons

2.2. OTEC plant model

In this study, we utilized a model previously created to represent a closed-cycle plant with a net power output of 100MW and a gross power output of 150MW. Given that the fish farm's energy demand is significantly lower than this capacity, a scaling factor was applied to determine the net output of smaller OTEC plants. This model determines the net power output of a single OTEC plant based on water temperatures and the length of the cold-water pipe.

In this model, the net power production (P_{Net}) of the OTEC system is calculated using Equation (1) which consists of three components: the gross power (P_{Gross}), determined by the thermodynamic equations governing the Rankine cycle; variable losses (L_{Var}), linked to cold water pumping; and fixed losses (L_{Fixed}), associated with other pumping and transmission activities within the plant:

$$P_{Net}(MW) = P_{Gross} - L_{Fixed} - L_{var} \quad (1)$$

where gross power has been found to be directly proportional to the temperature difference (ΔT) between the surface (T_s) and cold deep water (T_D) and is calculated using the linear function:

$$P_{Gross}(MW) = 13.89\Delta T - 149.71 \quad (2)$$

L_{Fixed} is estimated to be 42.7MW and is the sum of cold-water intake power loss, condenser, distribution pumping loss, and ammonia pumping loss within the process. L_{var} is the total variable loss factor and is the sum of pipe friction and static head losses. This parameter is a function of the depth of the cold water, and the final formula is as follows:

$$L_{var}(MW) = 0.0038d + 4.488 (5.234 \times 10^{-10}d^3 - 1.378 \times 10^{-6}d^2 + 1.313 \times 10^{-3}d^{-3} - 0.6541) \times \left(\frac{-0.00599T_s^2 + 0.031T_s + 1025}{-0.00599(T_s - \Delta T)^2 + 0.031(T_s - \Delta T) + 1025} - 1 \right) \times d \quad (3)$$

where d is the cold-water pipe depth [9].

OTEC operates most efficiently with temperature differentials of at least 20°C. Therefore, selecting an optimal site is crucial to ensure the performance of the OTEC plant. An assessment of Florida's OTEC resources suggests that an OTEC plant equipped with a 1000-meter-long Cold Water Pipe (CWP) would produce the highest power output when located at 23°41.6'N, 82°04.8'W [10]. Daily HYCOM thermal data was not available for this location, therefore, data for the nearest location (20°02.4'N, 81°33.6'W) with the annual average temperature difference of 23.1°C are used for further calculations.

2.3. Battery energy system model

State of Charge (SoC) is a vital parameter for Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) and plays a key role in energy management. It primarily indicates the remaining capacity of the BES, defined as the ratio of the remaining capacity to the rated capacity under identical conditions after being discharged at a specific current rate. In this study, the SoC of the BES was calculated using the ampere-hour integral method, commonly known as the Coulomb counting method, as follows [11]:

$$SoC(t) = SoC(t-1) + \frac{1}{Q_{bat, rated}} \int \eta_c \frac{P_{bat}(t)dt}{N_B \times V_{bat}} \quad (4)$$

where $SoC(t)$ and $SoC(t - 1)$ represent the state of charge at the current and previous steps, respectively. $Q_{bat, rated}$ denotes the rated capacity of the BES (kAh); $P_{bat}(t)$ is the power of the BES (kW); η_c represents the Coulombic efficiency (%); V_{bat} is the rated voltage of the BES (V), and N_B is the total number of batteries.

The BES can operate in both charging and discharging modes, depending on the power mismatch within the system. When the OTEC power output exceeds the load demand, the BES will absorb and store the excess energy. Conversely, when the load demand surpasses the OTEC power output, the BES will discharge its stored energy to meet the deficit.

Over-discharge must be prevented to maximize battery lifespan. Therefore, at any given hour t , the $SoC(t)$ is constrained by the following limits [12]:

$$(1 - DOD) \leq SoC(t) \leq 1 \quad (5)$$

where DOD represents the maximum depth of discharge. Table 1 shows the technical specifications of the battery model chosen for this study.

Table 1. Technical parameters of BES system [11]

Parameter	Rated Capacity (Ah)	Rated Voltage (V)	DoD (%)	Coulombic efficiency (%)
Value	300	12	70	85

2.4. Diesel generator model

As a backup power source, the diesel generator starts to work when OTEC generated power is insufficient and the energy in the storage system reaches its minimum level. In this scenario, the diesel generator operates to meet the power shortfall. The fuel consumption of the diesel generator, denoted as $Fuel_{DG} (l/h)$, is a function of the diesel generator output power and is expressed by the following equation:

$$Fuel_{DG} = a \times P_{DG} + b \times P_{DG}^{Rated} \quad (6)$$

where P_{DG}^{Rated} represents the rated power, P_{DG} is the output power of the diesel generator, and $a = 0.246 (l/kWh)$ and $b = 0.0845 (l/kWh)$ are the coefficients of the fuel consumption curve [13].

3. Techno-economic assessment

3.1. Loss of power supply probability (LPSP) and reliability index (RI)

The optimal sizing methodology involves determining the optimal number of batteries and OTEC capacity based on optimization principles, taking into account the system's reliability which depends on LPSP and the system's cost [11]. loss as expressed by the following expressions:

$$LPSP = \frac{E_{shortage}}{E_{load}} \quad (7)$$

where $E_{shortage}$ and E_{load} are the annual energy shortage and the annual load demand (kWh), respectively.

The RI is utilized to measure the power supply reliability of an energy system. It can be determined using the LPSP as follows:

$$RI = 100\% - (LPSP \times 100)\% = \quad (8)$$

where $RI=100\%$ signifies that the system can fully meet load demand, while a value closer to 0 indicates that the energy provided by the system falls short of meeting the entire load demand. Fish farms require a reliable and uninterrupted power supply, as any disruption could result in the complete failure of farm operations and the loss of all yields. Therefore, in this study, it is assumed that RI is equal to 100%.

3.2. Levelized cost of energy (LCOE)

Successful installation of an OTEC-diesel system with battery energy storage requires not only technical considerations but also economic evaluation. Current literature predominantly utilizes the LCOE to evaluate the cost of energy, expressed in \$/kWh. $LCOE_{load}$ refers to the overall cost incurred throughout the entire lifespan of an investment, divided by the total amount of energy consumed by that investment. Thus, the LCOE can be mathematically represented as:

$$LCOE_{load} = \frac{I_0 + \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{(C_n + F_n)}{(1+r)^n} + C_{reinv}}{\sum_{n=1}^N \frac{(E_{utilized}(1-d)^n)}{(1+r)^n}} \quad (9)$$

where I_0 represents the investment cost (\$) which includes the costs of OTEC, BES, and diesel generator; C_n is the fuel cost as well as operation and maintenance (O&M) cost (\$) in year n ; C_{reinv} stands for the reinvestment cost (\$) since certain components within the system, such as the BES and diesel generator, require replacement due to having a shorter lifespan compared to the project lifetime; $E_{generated}$ signifies the annual energy production of the system (kWh); d denotes the annual degradation rate (0.5%) in the efficiency of the system's component; r indicates the discount rate (9%); and N represents the project's lifetime (25 years) [11].

4. Results

A summary of the design parameters and specifications of components in the system for techno-economic optimization are described in Table 2. For fuel delivery, it is assumed that the same vessel for food and harvest is used for fuel delivery, and the day rate for a vessel and 2 crew is \$4000.

Table 2. Specifications and associated costs of the components

Description	OTEC [14]	BES [11]	DG [11]
Unit Cost (\$/kW)	$61980 \times (\text{Plant size}(MW))^{-0.349}$	190	230
O&M Cost	5.5% of unit cost	2% of unit cost	0.1 \$/h
Life Span	25 years	5 years	15,000 hours
Fuel Cost (including delivery)	-	-	11.12 \$/Gal

In our study, we examined three distinct scenarios for optimal sizing of the system. Initially, we analyzed a scenario where only a diesel generator was employed (reference scenario). Subsequently, we evaluated the OTEC with BES for the fish farm introduced in section 2.1. Finally, we explored a third scenario involving a fish farm ten times larger than the one used in the second scenario. The optimal result of each system configuration based on techno-economic indicators is shown in Table 3. CI is the curtailment index and defined as the ratio between the annual energy wastage and the annual energy generation.

As we can see, in the first scenario focusing on the diesel generator alone, the system relies solely on a 305kW generator, achieving a 100% reliability index and no curtailment issues. In the small-scale fish farm scenario, the configuration maintains a high reliability index at 100%, with a noteworthy CI of 95%. In addition, the LCOE stands at \$6.89 per kWh, which is twice the reference scenario. The higher LCOE is mainly due to the very high capital cost of OTEC. For 80kW OTEC, the capital cost of OTEC system is 149,469 \$/kW, which leads to a total cost of approximately 12 million dollars. For the large-scale fish farm scenario, incorporating a 750kW OTEC system, the capital cost is 68,526 \$/kW, which leads to a total cost of less than 52 million dollars. These costs significantly exceed those suggested in the literature for small-scale OTEC projects, indicating that the proposed cost estimation formula may be overestimating expenses for smaller OTEC systems. This system can uphold 100% RI and an 85% curtailment index along with a lower LCOE at \$3.28 per kWh. The reduced LCOE is largely attributed to the significantly lower capital cost for the 750kW OTEC system, which is nearly half that of the 80kW system. The considerable increase in the curtailment index when integrating OTEC and BES can be linked to a significant peak demand of 200kW compared to a lesser baseload of 11kW, resulting in system oversizing. Furthermore, the capital cost of OTEC systems follows a power function, resulting in significant cost variations for capacities below 1MW. This non-linear relationship means that small changes in OTEC capacity can lead to rapid and substantial changes in capital costs, making economic feasibility a critical consideration for smaller-scale implementations.

Table 3. Optimal result for each energy system configuration

Scenario	OTEC (kW)	Battery (kAh)	DG (kW)	RI (%)	CI (%)	LCOE (\$/kWh)
Diesel Generator alone	0	0	305	100%	0	3.40
Small-scale fish farm	80kW	52	31	100%	95%	6.89
Large-scale fish farm	750kW	559	425	100%	85%	3.28

5. Conclusion

This study presents an analysis of optimal sizing for a hybrid OTEC-diesel energy system with battery storage tailored for fish farming applications. The results underscore the effectiveness of the proposed system to meet the energy demands of fish farms while minimizing the levelized cost of energy. In the reference scenario, which relies solely on a diesel generator, results in an LCOE of \$3.40 per kWh. For the small-scale fish farm scenario, the introduction of an 80kW OTEC system, 52kAh of battery storage, and a 31kW diesel generator maintains a reliability index of 100% but incurs a higher LCOE of \$6.89 per kWh and a substantial CI of 95%. Conversely, the large-scale fish farm scenario, which incorporates a 750kW OTEC system, achieves the same RI with an improved CI of 85%

and, most importantly, a lower LCOE of \$3.28 per kWh. This demonstrates that scaling up the hybrid system not only reduced the LCOE but also reduced the energy wastage, making it a more economically viable solution for large-scale fish farming operations.

One key benefit of employing renewable energy sources is the mitigation of carbon emissions. Consequently, future research should consider the social cost of carbon. Additionally, incorporating a more detailed model for system components—such as accounting for the minimum load of diesel generators, the self-discharge rate of batteries, or a detailed model for OTEC, particularly for small-scale applications—could improve the accuracy of results. While OTEC systems are currently expensive, the existing capital cost model is primarily developed for systems larger than 1MW, resulting in an overestimation of costs for smaller-scale OTEC projects. Therefore, refining the economic model to better reflect the costs associated with smaller OTEC systems is essential. Nevertheless, the findings of this study highlight the potential for hybrid OTEC-Diesel systems with battery storage to support sustainable and cost-effective energy solutions in the offshore aquaculture industry.

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